

PROGRAM GUIDE

CITIZEN SCIENCE FOR HEALTH CONFERENCE

29 OCT - 1 NOV 2023

UNIVERSITY OF TWENTE.

DEAR PARTICIPANTS,

The seed for the inaugural global Citizen Science for Health conference, of which you are now holding the program booklet, was sown during the European Citizen Science Association (ECSA) conference in Berlin in 2022.

The ECSA Citizen Science for Health Working Group was first established in 2020 after the need for this new research field was highlighted from several angles. Two years later the working group met live during the conference in Berlin. The enthusiasm was overwhelming: let many flowers bloom. One of the seeds sown in Berlin was for a global conference on Citizen Science for Health. An opportunity to share knowledge gained in recent years, establish new connections and collaborate in this fast-growing field. We have now seen our fantasy become reality and a dream come true.

We were delighted with the submissions and overjoyed to see people from all over the world sign up. Together, we opted for an interactive, open format with

solution rooms & showcases, workshops and posters. The conference will be hosted at the University of Twente (NL), at DesignLab and TechMed Centre. During the conference, visitors can go on wellbeing around the campus and its beautiful natural surroundings. We hope to meet you in person at the campus of the University of Twente.

On Sunday, we will kick off the conference with a unique citizen day (in Dutch), supported by the Radboud Fund, followed by our first keynote speakers.

On Monday and Tuesday, the program is full of interesting sessions and events, but we left plenty of time to meet each other, to reflect and discuss, and to have fun as well! For the conference dinner and music, we will move to the city of Enschede.

People interested in the organizational aspects of Citizen Science are welcome to join *Grounding Citizen Science in Research Institutions*, the joint final conference of the EU-projects TIME4CS and INCENTIVE on Wednesday, November 1.

If you have any questions, please don't hesitate to contact the organizers. We hope you find

inspiration at this inaugural edition of the CS4H conference.

Dr. Sabine Wildevuur
CS4H conference chair

On behalf of the Scientific and Program Committee, and the ECSA Citizen Science for Health Working Group.

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THE ORGANIZING COMMITTEE

Sabine Wildevuur, PhD
Conference chair

Ria Wolkorte, PhD
Chair scientific committee

Michelle de Boer, MSc
General conference organizer

Lieke Heesink, PhD
Chair scientific committee

Rhoda Schuling, PhD
Chair organizational committee

Berry van Holland, PhD
Member

Kris Bevelander, PhD
Chair program committee

Joana Magalhães, PhD
Member

**Bastian Greshake
Tzovaras, PhD
Member**

**Isabelle Bonhoure, PhD
Member**

**Lea den Broeder, PhD
Member**

**Egbert Siebrand, MSc
Member**

**Gaston Remmers, PhD
Member**

**Linnea Marie Sjöberg,
MSc
Member**

**Martijn de Groot, PhD
Member**

**Renske van Wijk, PhD
Member**

**We are very grateful for the
support of DesignLab's Dream
Team students:**

**İlayda Hotamış,
Roussi Roussev,
Riki Ogawa and others**

PRACTICALITIES

BUILDINGS

The conference takes place in three different buildings located at the campus of University of Twente, Enschede: U Park hotel (Sunday), TechMed Centre (Monday and Tuesday), and DesignLab (Monday and Tuesday).

U Park hotel

The U Park hotel is located on the University of Twente campus, between the cities of Enschede and Hengelo and is easily accessible by public transport (train and bus) and by car.

Visiting address
De Veldmaat 8
7522 NM Enschede

DesignLab and TechMed Centre

Parking: Hengelosestraat 500
7521 AN Enschede

DesignLab and TechMed Centre are located next to each other at the central square (O&O Plein) of the University of Twente. You can access DesignLab from the side of the Gallery building.

DIRECTIONS

Scan the QR code below for directions to the different buildings.

REGISTRATION

Sunday: 17.00 – 18.00 (U Park hotel)

Monday: 8.30 - 9.15 (TechMed Centre)

If you have any questions or if you want to register on Tuesday, you can visit the information desk at the TechMed Centre.

INTERNET ACCESS

Free internet access is assured on the university campus, and in all rooms of DesignLab and TechMed Centre. Select the WLAN network “Enschede Stad van nu” and open your browser. First you will see a page on which you will be requested to accept the conditions for the use of wireless internet.

The Eduroam network is available on many universities and schools throughout the world. If you are a student or staff of such school, you can log into this network by using the credentials from your home institutions.

AV-EQUIPMENT

Each session room is equipped with a projector and connecting cables. Please bring your own laptop and arrive early to prepare your presentations to ensure a smooth start of the sessions. If a specific piece of equipment is needed, then please refer to the front desk of the building where your presentation is conducted.

JOIN THE DISCUSSION ONLINE

Use hashtag **#CitSci4Health23**

CONFERENCE DINNER

The conference dinner is on Monday evening, from 19h00-23h00 at the Twentsche Foodhal, Performance Factory, Hoge Bothofstraat 39a, Enschede. Dinner and starting drinks are included for those who bought a conference ticket. Additional drinks are at your own expense. Free bus transportation is arranged from the conference venue to the Twentsche Foodhal and back again to the campus.

We cordially invite you to visit the “surgical food experience” at the beginning of the dinner.

ZENODO FOR CONFERENCE MATERIALS

We urge you to upload conference material to Zenodo, see the conference website for more information and visit the community at <https://zenodo.org/communities/cs4h-conference-2023/>

WALKING ROUTES

Feel free at any time to take one of our walking routes around the campus. We have set up three different routes for you: one of 10, 15 or 30 minutes. Maps are available at the information desk.

PLENARY KEYNOTE SESSIONS

SUNDAY

Sunday at 18.00

KEYNOTE **Personal Science:
A Practical Approach Bringing
the Virtues of Citizen Science
Forward Into Digital Health**

Gary Wolf

Gary is an American author, researcher and co-founder of the Quantified Self, an international collaboration among users and makers of self-tracking tools. Wolf is currently the director of Article 27, a nonprofit foundation supporting participation in science. He is a member of the Personal Science Research Group, and, with colleagues, has contributed to numerous projects

and publications on self-research and self-tracking.

Sara Riggare

Sara is a Swedish researcher at Uppsala University and Parkinson's disease advocate who has made significant contributions to the field of healthcare and patient empowerment. With a background in engineering and a PhD in medical science, she combines her unique perspectives to bridge the gap between patients and healthcare professionals. Sara is also a member of the Personal Science Research Group.

MONDAY

Monday at 9.45

KEYNOTE **The Participatory Turn in Health Research. Its Roots, Methods, Ethics, Validity and Future**

Tineke Abma

Tineke is Executive-Director of Leyden Academy of Vitality and Ageing and Professor 'Participation of Older People' at the department of Public Health & Primary Care at Leiden University Medical Centre. She has been researching themes closely related to patient participation, participatory action research, ethics and diversity in the context of healthcare.

TUESDAY

Tuesday at 11.00

KEYNOTE **First responders in public health crises: experiences from Africa and reflections on citizen engagement**

Susannah Mayhew

Susannah is professor in Health Policy, Systems and Reproductive Health at the London School of Hygiene & Tropical Medicine. Her work has included research on perspectives of healthcare providers and health service users on reproductive health issues in Africa and Asia, the importance of learning from first responders during Sierra Leone's Ebola crisis, and how villagers in rural Uganda are adapting to the challenges of climate change.

MAP

ENSCHEDÉ

MAP

DESIGNLAB

DESIGNLAB MAP

Hengelo

Station Enschede Kennispark

HENGELSESTRAAT

UNIVERSITY OF TWENTE CAMPUS

Enschede

SUPPORTING PARTNERS

DESIGNLAB

DesignLab is an eco-system facilitating creative collaboration and knowledge transfer between researchers, societal organizations, students, and citizens. They value plural perspectives and expertise from individuals as well as organizations – nurturing collaborative projects that transcend disciplinary and professional domains. In their ecosystem anyone can become an agent of change. Their activities are shaped by the theme of Responsible Futuring – a unique approach towards science-based innovation to design ethically for society.

DUTCH RESEARCH COUNCIL (NWO)

The Dutch Research Council (NWO) is one of the most important science funding bodies in the Netherlands and realizes quality and innovation in science. Each year, NWO invests almost 1 billion euros in curiosity-driven research, research related to societal challenges and research infrastructure.

ECSA

The European Citizen Science Association (ECSA) is a membership organization set up in 2014. Their main goals are to increase the democratization of science, encourage the growth of citizen science in Europe, and support the participation of the general public in research processes across the natural sciences, social sciences, humanities, and the arts. Their mission is to make science and research open, accessible and valuable for everyone.

INCENTIVE

INCENTIVE is a cross-national 3-year long project supported by the European Union within the framework of the Horizon 2020 program. It aims to demonstrate the potential of citizen science through the co-creation, establishment and assessment of Citizen Science Hubs in four European Universities: University of Twente (the Netherlands),

Autonomous University of Barcelona (Spain), Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (Greece) and Vilnius Gediminas Technical University (Lithuania).

RADBOUD FUND

As a society, we are facing a number of challenges. Our planet is depleting, people are under pressure, and the healthcare system is not sustainable. Finding a solution to these issues can be achieved through research. The Radboud Fund provides the time and resources necessary for researchers to address these challenges. The fund plays a pivotal role in the birth of scientific and medical breakthroughs, supporting innovative ideas.

UNIVERSITY OF TWENTE

The University of Twente is a pioneer in fusing technology, science and engineering with social sciences to impact the world around us. Their driving force as students, scientists and educators is a deep sense of connection with people who share a curious, entrepreneurial spirit.

**UNIVERSITY
OF TWENTE.**

PROGRAM OVERVIEW

SUNDAY, OCTOBER 29
U PARK HOTEL

13:00 - 17:00

DUTCH CITIZEN DAY

17:00 – 20:30

Registration and welcome

17:00 – 18:00

REGISTRATION AND WELCOMING

17:00 – 18:00

**Dutch Heart Foundation and
Citizen Science: check your vital
signs**

18:00 – 19:15

**OPENING KEYNOTE SPEAKERS:
GARY WOLF & SARA RIGGARE**

19:15 – 20:30

NETWORKING AND DRINKS

MONDAY, OCTOBER 30

TECHMED CENTRE AND DESIGNLAB

8:30 – 10:45

REGISTRATION, OPENING AND KEYNOTE

8:30 – 9:15

Registration / put up poster

ROOM Atrium (TMC)

9:15 – 9:45

Opening

ROOM TL2275 (TMC)

9:45 – 10:45

KEYNOTE SPEAKER: TINEKE ABMA

ROOM TL2275 (TMC)

10:45 – 11:15

COFFEE BREAK

ROOM Atrium (TMC)

SESSIONS

11:15 – 12:45

WORKSHOP SESSION I (90 MINS) & SOLUTION ROOMS I (20 MINS)

1. How to measure impact on participants' learning in citizen science projects?

Havinga, P.

ROOM TL2107 (TMC)

2. The Challenges of Impact Assessment in Citizen Science Health Studies

Schaefer, T.

ROOM TL2187 (TMC)

3. Identifying Opportunities for Funders to Promote the Use of Citizen Science in Health Research

Mintz, E.

ROOM TL2389 (TMC)

4. Guidelines and oversight: developing a framework for ethical citizen science for health

Wolkorte, R.

ROOM TL1336 (TMC)

MONDAY, OCTOBER 30 TECHMED CENTRE AND DESIGNLAB

5. Applying the 'vision in design' methodology in technology development with and for people in vulnerable health positions

Heijster, H.

ROOM TL2148 (TMC)

6. The games we play: Exploring implicit processes in collaboration through arts-based methods.

Breed, M.

ROOM Inform (DL)

7. Active Living at your workplace: How to get started!

Sjöberg, L.M.

ROOM Learn-X (DL)

8. Patient-driven research communities in health: mapping international bottom-up approaches

Remmers, G.

ROOM Invite (DL)

12:45 – 14:00

LUNCH

12:45 – 14:00

Presentation European Citizen Science Association

ROOM Atrium (TMC)

12:45 – 14:00

Dutch Heart Foundation and Citizen Science: check your vital signs

ROOM TL1133 (TMC)

13:30 – 13:45

**Network walk
Start from Atrium**

ROOM (TMC)

14:00 – 14:20

**SOLUTION ROOMS II &
SHOWCASES I SESSIONS**

9. Taking the next step: How to face the challenges of moving towards Citizen Science?

te Braake, E.

ROOM TL2107 (TMC)

MONDAY, OCTOBER 30 TECHMED CENTRE AND DESIGNLAB

10. Effective communication about health among a various group of stakeholders: language use, power relations, and vulnerability

ter Bogt, M.

ROOM TL2187 (TMC)

11. Managing boundaries between researchers and patients: A balancing act

Fruytier, S.

ROOM TL2389 (TMC)

12. A science of engagement in health research and innovation: New roles for citizen scientists as peer researchers who bring a new patient research voice to health transformation.

Marlett, N.

ROOM TL1251 (TMC)

13. Establishing a global typology for citizen engagement in health research

Nielssen, I

ROOM Invite (DL)

14. Optimizing the Wisdom of the Crowd for Classification Tasks

Michelucci, P.

ROOM Inform (DL)

15. The OIS Impact Model: Planning and assessing the impact of co-creation in research

Mahve-Beydokhti, M.

ROOM Learn-X (DL)

16. Framework for active involvement in participatory eHealth research

Oberschmidt, K.

ROOM Inspire (DL)

14:30 – 14:50

SHOWCASES II & SOLUTIONS ROOMS III

17. A showcase for Science of Engagement (SoE) in health research and innovation as part of Citizen Science, Community Health Research and Patient Engagement Research platforms.

Marlett, N.

ROOM Inform

MONDAY, OCTOBER 30 TECHMED CENTRE AND DESIGNLAB

18. Patient and Community Engagement Research (PaCER)-an experiential based, participatory health research methodology program

Nielssen, I.

ROOM TL2148

19. "CoAct for Mental Health" Chatbot: a practical demonstration of a "humans to humans" chatbot reinterpreted for citizen social science.

Bonhoure, I.

ROOM Learn-X

20. How to measure impact of citizen science in public health projects?

van Holland, B.

ROOM Play

21. Community engagement during the COVID-19 crisis: what can we learn from this?

den Broeder, L.

ROOM TL2107

22. Canceled

23. Participatory research into clown visits in long-term care: How to better engage persons with dementia in the research process?

de Kock, L. & Groot, B.

ROOM TL1251

**15.00 – 15:30
COFFEE BREAK**

ROOM Atrium (TMC)

**15:30 – 17:00
WORKSHOP SESSION II**

24. Digital Storytelling (DST) in Health Research

Zelinsky, S.

ROOM TL1336 (TMC)

25. Mapping accessibility of the UT campus for people with disabilities

Flacke, J.

ROOM TL2148 (TMC)

MONDAY, OCTOBER 30 TECHMED CENTRE AND DESIGNLAB

26. Citizen Science for Health: Exploring Stakeholders' Different Perspectives

Maschino, J.

ROOM Learn-X (DL)

27. Citizen science empowered public spaces: chances and challenges for designing AI-based Artworks to enhance human encounters and social health in public space.

van Buuren, L.

ROOM Inspire (DL)

28. Tools to meaningfully involve citizen scientists and professionals

Wagemakers, A.

ROOM Inform (DL)

52. Á la recherche du santé perdue: exploring tech-based solutions through co-creation to support quality of life in transitions following the diagnosis of an invisible disability

Toso, F.

ROOM Invite (DL)

17:00 – 18:00 POSTER SESSION I & REFRESHMENTS

SESSIONS

29-33

Theme: Participatory approaches

29. IdeenLauf - Social impulses for science and research policy

Waltersbacher, E.

ROOM Atrium (TMC)

30. Engaging Young People as Co-researchers in Mental Health research during the COVID-19 crisis: Ethical and Practical reflections

Maindal, N. & Kragh, G.

ROOM Atrium (TMC)

31. Participating in Place-Based Citizen Science: The Impact on Subjective Well-being of Refugee Youth

Egorova, E.

ROOM Atrium (TMC)

MONDAY, OCTOBER 30 TECHMED CENTRE AND DESIGNLAB

32. Engaging Older Adults in Large-Scale Co-Design Activities for late-life Loneliness: A Citizen Science Approach

Tunc, S.

ROOM Atrium (TMC)

33. Involving patients via the "Austrian Patient Council"

Teufel, A.

ROOM Atrium (TMC)

34-36

Theme: Personal science

34. What are the barriers and supports to a return to health for those living with long COVID? - a patient-led, peer-to-peer qualitative project.

Nielsen, I.

ROOM Atrium (TMC)

35. IBD Partnerships: A Patient-Led Peer to Peer project using arts based approaches to improve shared decision making

Zelinsky, S.

ROOM Atrium (TMC)

36. Towards the baseline of health research infrastructure: the development of the Self Research Network Netherlands (Z.O.N.N.)

Remmers, G.

ROOM Atrium (TMC)

37-45

Theme: Crowdsourcing knowledge

37. Beta Catchers: Crowd-Powered Analysis of Neuropathology for Alzheimer's Disease Research

Michelucci, P.

ROOM Atrium (TMC)

38. Defining research priorities in the stoma care

Villa, G.

ROOM Atrium (TMC)

39. Research agenda's truly reflecting patients' needs: the case of the Dutch Brain Foundation

Pittens, C.

ROOM Atrium (TMC)

MONDAY, OCTOBER 30 TECHMED CENTRE AND DESIGNLAB

40. Citizen Science for Understanding the Health and Well-being of Fishers: Empirical Insights for Sustainable Coastal Communities

Elegbede, I.

ROOM Atrium (TMC)

41. Engaging citizens in environmental health monitoring

Tavantzis, I.

ROOM Atrium (TMC)

42. Xaire: how a large-scale air quality citizen science campaign can improve health quality assessments and promote community knowledge and collective action

Bonhoure, I.

ROOM Atrium (TMC)

43. Health promotion and homelessness in Germany. Co-defining challenges, co-designing methods, co-creating solutions

Anthonj, C.

ROOM Atrium (TMC)

44. SDG OLYMPIAD

Mondardini, R.

ROOM Atrium (TMC)

45. Highlights of the need for a Science of Engagement (SoE) in health research and innovation for Citizen Science

Marlett, N.

ROOM Atrium (TMC)

46-47

Theme: Insights and participation

46. Citizen Science 4 Health: SDU Moves

Sjöberg, L.M.

ROOM Atrium (TMC)

47. Enhancing Informed Consent in Citizen Science for Healthcare: Incorporating Quality Labels into Consent Forms

van Dop, Y. & Wilmont, I.

ROOM Atrium (TMC)

MONDAY, OCTOBER 30

CONFERENCE DINER AT TWENTSCHE FOODHAL

18:10 – 19:00

**TRANSPORT TO CONFERENCE
DINNER**

18:10 Group 1:

**Bus transport or walk to
conference dinner**

18:35 Group 2:

**Bus transport to conference
dinner**

**Assembly point: main entrance
TechMed Centre**

19:00 - 23:00

**CONFERENCE DINNER AND
PARTY TWENTSCHE FOODHAL**

23:00

Transport back to campus

23:00 Group 1:

Bus transport back to campus

23:30 Group 2:

Bus transport back to campus

**Assembly point: main entrance
Twentsche Foodhal**

TUESDAY, OCTOBER 31

TECHMED CENTRE AND DESIGNLAB

8:30 – 9:00

DAY 3 OPENING

Registration / put up poster

ROOM Atrium (TMC)

9:00 – 10:30

WORKSHOP SESSIONS III

48. Science Citizenship: The Case of Citizen Science NOW

Vonk, J.

ROOM TL1336 (TMC)

49. Citizen Science Incubator - Getting your project off the ground

Michelucci, P.

ROOM TL2148 (TMC)

50. Building participative environments

Slager, M.

ROOM Inform (DL)

51. Partnership readiness and holding safe spaces in health research

Zelinsky, S.

ROOM Learn-X (DL)

52. See page 23

53. Exploring the interrelation of citizen science and patient involvement

Vroonland, E.

ROOM TL2187 (TMC)

10:30 – 11:00

Coffee break & refreshments

ROOM Atrium (TMC)

11:00 – 12:00

Keynote Speaker

Keynote speaker: Susannah

Mayhew

ROOM TL2275 (TMC)

12:15 – 12:35

SOLUTIONS ROOMS IV & SHOWCASES III

54. Science Citizenship - Exploring the Important Competences

Vonk, J.

ROOM Inform (DL)

55. Co-creation with vulnerable groups – a needs-driven, inclusive focus group methodology

Kastl, A.

ROOM Learn-X (DL)

TUESDAY, OCTOBER 31 TECHMED CENTRE AND DESIGNLAB

56. How to best integrate citizen science aspects in the implementation of the newly developed app for Intelligent Physical Exercise Training (IPET)?

Sjöberg, L.M.

ROOM Inspire (DL)

57. Expanding the role of experts-by-experience in citizen science

Elkhuizen, S.

ROOM TL2148 (TMC)

58. Citizen science with children

Jepkema, N.

ROOM Invite (DL)

59. Student wellbeing through Citizen Science; students, research & practice together

Schuling, R.

ROOM Play (DL)

60. Personal Science Wiki

Kloppenborg, K.

ROOM TL2107 (TMC)

61. VRbeelding: Improving citizens perceptions on dementia through a co-created Virtual Reality experience

ten Velde, G.

ROOM TL2187 (TMC)

62. A digital platform for citizen science

Boom, M.

ROOM TL2389 (TMC)

63. Inclusive Knowledge Translation and Dissemination in Patient-Oriented Research

Zelinsky, S.

ROOM TL1251 (TMC)

12:45 – 14:00

LUNCH

12:45 – 14:00

Presentation European Citizen Science Association

ROOM Atrium (TMC)

12:45 – 14:00

Dutch Heart Foundation and Citizen Science: check your vital signs

ROOM TL1133 (TMC)

TUESDAY, OCTOBER 31

TECHMED CENTRE AND DESIGNLAB

12.45-14.00

**Dutch Research Council (NWO):
Citizen science and societal
engagement in Open Science NL**

ROOM Room TL1336

13:30 – 13:45

**Network walk
Start from Atrium**

ROOM (TMC)

14:00 – 15:30

WORKSHOP SESSIONS IV

**64. Stumbling blocks & quality
criteria for youth participation**

Dedding, C.

ROOM TL1336 (TMC)

**65. Advancing on equitable and
inclusive health for women and
LGBTQIA+**

Magalhães, J.

ROOM TL2148 (TMC)

**66. Does Citizen Science for
Health need (more) engagement**

Slager, M.

ROOM Inform (DL)

**67. Personal Science and
Self-Tracking: Learning From
Continuous Blood Glucose Data**

Wolf, G.

ROOM Learn-X (DL)

**68. CoAct for Mental Health:
a hands-on workshop and a
conversation co-presented by
Co-Researchers and academics.**

Bonhoure, I.

ROOM Invite (DL)

**69. The Ethical Review of Citizen
Science in Health: what is an
appropriate review regime?**

Remmers, G.

ROOM Inspire (DL)

**70. A Patient Standpoint theory
for Citizen Science as an
example of Iterative Co Design
with marginalized, community
and health system outsiders**

Marlett, N.

ROOM TL2187 (TMC)

TUESDAY, OCTOBER 31 TECHMED CENTRE AND DESIGNLAB

15:30 – 16:30

POSTERS II & REFRESHMENTS

71-81

Theme: Insights and participation

71. Do researchers find it worthwhile engaging the public? Lessons learned from 'A Healthier Southern Denmark'

Overgaard, A.K.

ROOM Atrium (TMC)

72. How to ensure a collaborative priority setting in participatory health research? Reflections on defining events in the initial phase of collaboration.

Pedersen, E.L.

ROOM Atrium (TMC)

73. What is the problem with barriers to patient and public involvement in health research? A critical review

Rasmussen, L.N.

ROOM Atrium (TMC)

74. Exploring the role of experts-by-experience in community health promotion

Elkhuizen, S.

ROOM Atrium (TMC)

75. Co-designing for inclusion: Lessons from the AutSPACES project

Tzovaras, B.G.

ROOM Atrium (TMC)

76. Open Innovation in Science Impact Lab - Caring Communities for Future

Soyer, L.

ROOM Atrium (TMC)

77. Why Citizen Scientists Want to be Involved in Translational Medicine Research in the Fields of Endocrinology and Metabolic Diseases?

Sarwar Shah, S.G.

ROOM Atrium (TMC)

78. Participatory Approaches to change Health Systems: A Systematic Review of Involvement Levels

Marinus, J.D.

ROOM Atrium (TMC)

TUESDAY, OCTOBER 31

TECHMED CENTRE AND DESIGNLAB

79. Will cooperating with scientists increase high school students' scientific literacy?

Alving, B.E.

ROOM Atrium (TMC)

80. Ciência + Cidadã program in Portugal— health related citizen science projects

Leão, M.

ROOM Atrium (TMC)

81. It's time for researchers to meet Citizen Science! Institutional changes to embed Citizen Science in RPOs: the case of UniSR as an Implementer partner of the European project TIME4CS

Fedeli, M.

ROOM Atrium (TMC)

82-88

Theme: CS4H and technology

82. Toward Inclusive Approaches in the Design, Development, and Implementation of eHealth: Scoping Review Into the Intellectual Disability Sector

van Calis, J.

ROOM Atrium (TMC)

83. Making technology sensitive by identifying profiles of needs and interests of vulnerable care recipients using human-centered design

Heijster, H.

ROOM Atrium (TMC)

84. Associations Over Time Between Fatigue, Stress, Pain, Sleep and Activities in Rheumatoid Arthritis: A Citizen Science and Experience Sampling study

Wolkorte, R.

ROOM Atrium (TMC)

85. Identification of essential behavioral components in m-Health to optimize citizens engagement with a Physical Activity app

Sjöberg, L.M.

ROOM Atrium (TMC)

86. StomyCraft: A multichannel approach to support ostomy children and their families.

Villa, G.

ROOM Atrium (TMC)

TUESDAY, OCTOBER 31 TECHMED CENTRE AND DESIGNLAB

87. How to improve communication using AI and other information communication technologies

Bikaitė, S. & Skaržauskienė, A.

ROOM Atrium (TMC)

88. An emerging Job Chance for individuals on the autism spectrum, deaf and hard of hearing – Digital Revolution needs competent Employees for qualitative Annotation.

Köck, K.

ROOM Atrium (TMC)

89-92

Theme: Participatory approaches

89. Co-creating science communication and research with young people about their mental health during the COVID-19 pandemic

Maindal, N.

ROOM Atrium (TMC)

90. The role of body image of adolescents in their social media use – a photovoice study

Ganahl, K. & Häfele, E.

ROOM Atrium (TMC)

91. AChild – Austrian Children with Hearing Impairment – A participatory research design

Dall, M.

ROOM Atrium (TMC)

92. The Co-Researchers journey in CoAct for Mental Health

Assumpta Mateu, Amanda Figueras, Isabelle Bonheure

ROOM Atrium (TMC)e

93. *Theme: Personal science*

93. REIS: A Citizen Science journey for and with people with rheumatic conditions

Grünloh, C.

16:30 – 17:00

CLOSING

ROOM Atrium (TMC)

WEDNESDAY, NOVEMBER 1 DESIGNLAB

9:00 – 18:00

**Optional working groups and
Final conference**

9:00 – 10:30

**Optional: working group
sessions**

ROOM DesignLab

9:00 – 18:00

**INCENTIVE – TIME4CS joint
final conference (free to join)
“Grounding Citizen Science in
Research Institutions: Science
with and for Citizens”**

Registration via QR code below

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